

TAM QUESTIONNAIRE

- 0) What is your group?
- 1) What is your main focus in software development?.
- 2) How much time do you have working with software development?
- 3) How much time do you have working with agile methodologies?
- 4) In the agile teams I've participated in, I consider that the developers/designers shared the leadership of the team.
- 5) Before taking part in the experiment, how many times did you take on the role of PO in your professional career?
- 6) During the experiment, did you take on the role of PO?
- 7) I consider the role of PO as one of the team leaders
- 8) Before taking part in the experiment, how many times did you take on the role of SM in your professional career?
- 9) During the experiment, did you take on the role of SM?
- 10) I consider the SM role as one of the team leaders
- 11) [U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to better understand my team's performance.
- 12) [U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to improve my team's performance.
- 13) [U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to better reflect on my team's sub-items of teamwork (Communication, Coordination, Cohesion, Effort, Mutual Support, Balance of Contribution).
- 14) [U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to improve my team's sub-items of teamwork (Communication, Coordination, Cohesion, Effort, Mutual Support, Balance of Contribution).
- 15) [U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to generate Guiding Questions that added value to my team.
- 16) [U] Performing the Role Rotation ceremony allowed me to improve my sharing of leadership among team members.
- 17) [U] The Role Rotation ceremony was better than the Sprint Retrospective at making the team reflect on their teamwork.
- 18) [E] It was easy to learn and use the Role Rotation ceremony.
- 19) [E] I find it easy to understand the Role Rotation ceremony.
- 20) [E] I find it easy to apply the Role Rotation ceremony.
- 21) [E] Using the Role Rotation ceremony made it easier to do my job.
- 22) [E] Using the Role Rotation ceremony made it easier for team members to share leadership.
- 23) Do you have any comments on the Role Rotation ceremony, its use and/or implementation?
- 24) Do you have any suggestions for improving the Role Rotation ceremony?
- 25) Would you like to share any additional material that you generated during the experiment?